

USING OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE PROCESS TEACNING ENGLISH

Toreniyazova Ziuarkhan Satniyazovna

Karakalpak Institute of Agriculture and Agro technologies,

Assistant teacher

ziuarxan10081975@gmail.com

Annotation: The article discusses the effectiveness of teaching English by interactive methods, which is necessary to form and develop students' communicative skills.

Key words: interactive methods, webinar, video conference, video lecture, virtual consultation.

At present, the English language is of great importance in the system of intercultural communications of various peoples of the world - it is directly involved in the formation and development of cultural, educational, political and socio-economic ties in the international arena. Recently, the role of the English language in the process of integrating educational and scientific organizations into the world community has noticeably increased. In this regard, there is a need to use modern forms and methods of teaching a foreign language, which ensure the most effective implementation of the training program, including for research scientists. The introduction of interactive forms of education is one of the most important areas for improving the preparation of students in modern universities. The quality of education is determined by the state and effectiveness of the educational process of teaching, its compliance with the needs and expectations of society and implies a social component, which includes the formation of an intellectually developed personality with a positive motivation for self-development. For a teacher of the new time, it is not enough to be competent in his field of knowledge, it is necessary to use methodological innovations

in the educational process, which today are associated with the use of interactive teaching methods.

However, the “basic element” is the methods and techniques of teaching a foreign language, which the teacher uses in the classroom, working directly with students. Knowledge and possession of language means by students, their use in communication depends on how effectively this material was presented, consolidated, worked out. The rapid development of computer technologies in recent years, as well as their intensive use in the educational process, has already led to some changes in the education system.

Modern pedagogy is rich in a whole arsenal of interactive methods, among which are the following: binary lecture (lecture-dialogue), briefing, webinar, video conference, video lecture, virtual consultation, virtual tutorial, debate, business game, discussion, dispute, simulation games, interactive (problem) lecture, information-problem lecture, case method (analysis of specific situations), colloquium, coaching (training), round table, lecture-press conference, Brainstorming method, portfolio method, group discussion, online seminar, problematic lecture, work in small groups, role-playing game, training, etc.

A webinar (from the words "web" and "seminar") is a "virtual" workshop organized using Internet technologies. The webinar is characterized by the main feature of the workshop - interactivity. You make a presentation, the audience asks questions, and you answer them. The easiest way to organize a webinar is to use the services of companies that specialize in providing these services. The main advantage of the webinar, as high availability for “visiting” the audience,

planning a convenient time for the webinar, presenting interesting information, interactive interaction between the teacher and students, convenience for students (without extraneous noise), plus notifying students in advance about the date and time of the webinar, etc.

A video conference is an area of information technology that simultaneously provides two-way transmission, processing, transformation and presentation of

interactive information over a distance in real time using computer hardware and software.

Videoconferencing is also referred to as a videoconferencing session. Video conferencing (abbreviated name VKS) is a telecommunications technology for interactive interaction between two or more remote subscribers, in which it is possible to exchange audio and video information between them in real time, taking into account the transmission of control data.

Video lecture. An abbreviated lecture filmed on film, supplemented with diagrams, tables, photographs and video clips illustrating the material presented in the lecture. A series of such lectures is well suited for distance learning, as well as for repeating the studied material.

Virtual consultation. Student self-study in the study of interactive educational materials allows him to obtain the main amount of educational information, and the completion of written tasks - to develop the skills of practical use of the concepts of the course in the study of his own experience.

The use of interactive methods in the educational process is effective and the peculiarity is that it arouses students' interest, contribute to the effective assimilation of educational material, provide feedback (audience response), form students' opinions and attitudes, form life skills, contribute to behavior change, etc.

List of references used

1. Arzumanyan L.S., Arakelyan L.A., Airapetyan A.A., Kazaryan M.G., Tepelikyan M.G. Features of the methodology of teaching a professionally oriented foreign language // Language and culture: Sat. mat. XXII intl. scientific-practical. conf. Novosibirsk, 2016. S. 20-24.
2. Zeer E.F., Pavlova A.M., Symanyuk E.E. Modernization of vocational education: Competence-based approach. – M.: MPSI, 2005. – 216 p.
3. Kononets A.N. Pedagogical modeling: new questions / A. N. Kononets // Innovative approaches to the organization of the educational process in a modern

technical university: Sat. method. tr. / ed. L. P. Lazareva; DVGUPS. - Khabarovsk: Publishing House of the Far East State University of Transportation, 2008. - S. 22-31.

4. Dvulichanskaya N. N. Interactive teaching methods as a means of forming key competencies // Science and education: electronic scientific and technical edition, 2011

5. Kobylska I Project methodology in teaching foreign languages students of non-linguistic universities // Collection of articles of the Scientific and Practical Conference "Intercultural Communication" - Omsk, 2006 - C 198-204